

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE SEEDS OF *WRIGHTIA TINCTORIA*.
CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE FIXED OIL

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The oil from the seeds of *Wrightia Tinctoria* has been examined and its constituents found out.

Wrightia Tinctoria or Indrajav or Mitha Indrajav, as it is known in Bengali and Hindi respectively, is a small deciduous tree belonging to the natural order of *Apocynaceae*. It is indigenous to Rajputana, Central Provinces, Deccan, {Konkan, S. M. Country, Ceylon and Burma and has been found to grow wild in tremendous profusion on the Western Ghats of Madras Presidency. The plant has been described by Kirtikar and Basu ("Indian Medicinal Plants", Part II, p. 1581) and also by K. M. Nadkarni ("Indian Materia Medica", p. 905). The plant, especially the bark and the seeds are regarded as highly medicinal in curing a variety of ailments. The bark and the seeds have been found to be equally effective and contain the same therapeutic properties as those of *Hollarrhena antidysentrica*. The general appearance of the seeds is such as to make their detection very difficult if mixed with the seeds of *Hollarrhena antidysentrica*. The seeds are used as an aphrodisiac and as a tonic they are given in seminal weakness.

The fixed oil from the seeds of the plant does not appear to have been previously examined although the fixed oil from a similar species of *Wrightia*, namely *Wrightia anamensis* has been examined by Margailien (*Compt. rend.*, 1931, 192, 373) with entirely different results. The chief fatty acid of this latter fixed oil has been described by the author as hydroxy-oleic acid, whereas in the present investigation the chief constituents have been found to be oleic and linolic acids. On pressing the seeds in the ghani, the oil was obtained in a yield of 30.49% as a deep red, highly viscous liquid. The oil has been worked up in details and its constituents have been described in the experimental portion of the paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

A sample of the seeds when burnt in a porcelain dish left on ignition 4.32% of a greyish white ash, consisting of 73.21% of water-soluble and 26.79% of water-insoluble inorganic material. The ash contained Ca, Fe, Na, K (traces), silica, chloride, sulphate, carbonate and phosphate.

Extraction of the Fixed Oil.—5.2 Kilos of the seed when pressed in a mill gave 1.585 Kilos of the oil in a yield of 30.49%. The crude oil, which had a deep red colour, was digested with animal charcoal and Fuller's earth and filtered hot. The oil after purification was a deep red, highly viscous, thick liquid, and possessed a characteristic odour of the drug. Even on prolonged standing no sediment or crystalline matter was deposited from the oil.

Examination of the Oil.—The oil does not contain any nitrogen or sulphur. It burns with a semi-sooty and odourless flame. In order to test the drying power

of the oil, a few drops of it were spread on a clean glass plate and kept at room temperature. After a fortnight the oil became very sticky proving it to be of the class of semi-drying oils. The physical and chemical constants of the oil are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Specific gravity (24°)	0.9552	Acetyl value	11.26
Refractive index (24°)	1.4940	Acid value	4.31
Viscosity (24°)	4.134	Riechert Missel value	0.81
Saponification value	180.1	Hehner value	92.6
Iodine value	87.6	Unsaponifiable matter	1.42%

The oil (200 g.) was then saponified with alcoholic potash as usual, the excess of alcohol distilled off and the soap dissolved in water, repeatedly extracted with ether in order to remove the unsaponifiable matter. The soap solution after the removal of the unsaponifiable matter decomposed with dilute sulphuric acid in presence of petrol-ether. The petroleum ether fatty acid layer was washed free from traces of sulphuric acid by water in a separating funnel, the solution dried (calcium chloride) and the solvent distilled off from a water-bath. The last traces of petroleum ether were removed from the mixed fatty acids thus obtained by heating on the water-bath and passing a current of carbon dioxide. Table II gives the constants of the mixed fatty acids.

TABLE II

Consistency	Semi solid
Neutralisation value	191.4
Mean mol. weight	293.1
Sp. gr. (64°)	0.8976
Iodine value	92.1

The mixed fatty acids (150 g.) were separated into saturated and unsaturated portions by Twitchell's modified lead salt-alcohol method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806). Table III gives the percentages, iodine values and mean molecular weights of the saturated and unsaturated fatty acids.

TABLE III

Acid.	% in mixed acids.	% in oil.	I. V.	Mean M. W.
Saturated	32.8	30.37	0.95	285.6
Unsaturated	67.2	62.23	134.7	281.4

Examination of the Unsaturated Acids.—The acids were treated with bromine according to the method of Jamieson and Baughmann (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 1198). Weighed amount (about 5 g.) of the liquid acids was dissolved in 100 c.c. of dry ether, the mixture was cooled in a freezing mixture to -10° and dry ethereal bromine was added drop by drop till it was in excess. The

temperature of the mixture was not allowed to rise above -5° during the addition of bromine. Then the mixture was allowed to stand for 2 hours at -10° , during this time no crystalline matter settled. Thus the absence of linolenic acid was confirmed. The ethereal liquid was, then freed from excess of bromine with an aqueous solution of sodium thiosulphate, in a separating-funnel. The solution was then dried (calcium chloride), filtered and the ether distilled off. The residue was dissolved in petrol ether (b. p. $40-60^{\circ}$) and cooled in a refrigerator when cubical crystals of linolic tetrabromide (m. p. 112°) separated out from the solution showing the presence of linolic acid. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness and the bromine content estimated. Table IV gives the results of analysis.

TABLE IV

Weight of the unsaturated acids taken	...	...	4.8592 g.
Weight of linolic tetrabromide insoluble in petrol ether	...	...	2.7212
Weight of residue (dibromide and tetrabromide)	...	...	6.2413
Bromine content of the residue	...	...	41.23%
Weight of tetrabromolinolic acid in the residue	...	...	2.3749 g.
Weight of total tetrabromolinolic acid	...	...	5.0981
Weight of oleic-dibromide in the residue	...	...	3.8664
Weight of linolic acid equivalent to tetrabromide	...	...	2.3781
Weight of oleic acid equivalent to dibromide	...	...	2.467

The percentage of oleic acid and linolic acid in the unsaturated acids, total fatty acids and in the original oil are given in Table V.

TABLE V

Acid.	Percentage in unsaturated acids.	Percentage in total fatty acids.	Percentage in original oil.
Linolic	48.94	32.88	30.46
Oleic	51.06	34.32	31.77

Examination of the Saturated Fatty Acids.—The saturated fatty acids obtained by the lead salt-alcohol method were freed from traces of liquid fatty acids by pressing on a porous plate. The acids thus obtained were almost colourless and melted between 60° and 69° . For the purpose of separation, the mixed acids were converted into their methyl esters by taking 40.2 g. of the saturated acids in a round bottomed flask, adding 170 g. of Merck's extra pure methyl alcohol and about 7g. of concentrated sulphuric acid, and the mixture was refluxed for about 4 hours on a water-bath. The excess of alcohol was then distilled off, the residue poured into about five times its volume of cold water, the liquid neutralised with sodium carbonate and the ester extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed first with distilled water, then with saturated solution of calcium chloride to remove any alcohol and finally with water. The ester was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and ether removed by distillation. The esters (41.7 g.), thus obtained, were then fractionated under reduced pressure. The saponification values of each fraction were determined and the mean molecular weight calculated. Table VI gives the results.

TABLE VI

Fraction No.	Boiling range Pressure 11 mm.	Wt. of distillate.	Sap. value.	Mean M. W.		Percentage of acids			
				Esters	Acids	from Sap value.	Myristic.	Palmitic.	Stearic.
1	160°-170°	2.7402 g.	208.7	268.7	254.7	4.06%	95.04%	...	...
2	170°-180°	11.2050	202.2	277.4	263.4	...	71.1	28.9%	...
3	180°-195°	18.0432	189.0	296.8	282.8	...	3.9	96.1	...
4	above 195°	9.6714	175.5	319.6	305.6	...	...	21.1	78.9%

The various fractions of the esters were separately hydrolysed with alcoholic caustic potash and the liberated acids repeatedly crystallised from alcohol. Palmitic, stearic and arachidic acids were thus obtained in almost pure condition and identified. The results are given in Table VII.

TABLE VII

Fraction No.	M p. of acid isolated.	Conclusion.
1	58-59°	Almost all palmitic acid
2	63.5-64.5°	Palmitic and stearic acid
3	68-69°	Practically all stearic with traces of palmitic acid.
4	74.5-75.5°	Mostly arachidic with traces of stearic acid.

Table VIII gives the composition of saturated fatty acids.

TABLE VIII

Acids.	Percentage in mixed saturated acids.	Percentage in total mixed fatty acids.	Percentage in oil.
Myristic	0.23	0.08	0.07
Palmitic	27.13	8.90	8.24
Stearic	54.29	17.80	18.48
Arachidic	18.35	6.02	5.58

Examination of the Unsaponifiable Matter.—The unsaponifiable matter obtained by ether extraction of the soap solution was washed repeatedly with water and the solvent distilled off. The substance crystallised in yellowish white crystals. On repeated crystallisation of the compound from alcohol it was obtained in fine colourless silky needles and flakes (m. p. 134.5°). The acetyl derivative melted at 125°. It is evidently sitosterol.

The seeds of *Wrightia tinctoria* have thus been found to contain 30.49% of a deep red semi-drying fixed oil, which contains the following constituents.

Glyceride of Linolic acid	31.82 %
" Oleic acid	33.98
" Myristic acid	0.07
" Palmitic acid	8.65
" Stearic acid	18.24
" Arachidic acid	5.82
" Unsaponifiable matter (mainly sitosterol)	1.42